

Fragments IV
by Brian Paul Kaess

1. 'Within these ancient texts were mysteries and secrets holier than fire.'
2. 'In his autobiography, the *dramatis personae* of Brian's life never cease to march across the eleven pages of this paper. A bit of a hagiography, it is therefore more crafted mirror than clear glass.'
3. 'It was so cold and foggy one January morning in Mexico (January 11, 2026), I should've read a Stephen King novel! No central heating, man- just blankets and cats! Brrrr!'
4. 'Perhaps our Cat Nieve was not the 'fiercest of the Lion's Den' as they once said of Hannibal, but she was certainly the hungriest!'
5. 'After having been Brian's stepson for a number of years, and having grown up to become a U.S. Army veteran of both Iraq and Afghanistan- even being awarded the Purple Heart- SSG Steven Ray Ellsberry must have felt like Scipio Africanus' adoptive grandson, called Scipio the Younger, who went on to raze Carthage in the third Punic War.'
6. 'Me, I had my fist up like Peter Fonda at the end of *Future World* (1976) when I left Chicago in 2006!'
7. 'The embers of protest burn brightly in Iran and no matter how many times the regime tried to stamp them out, they continued to glow, until at last it is nothing less than a blazing fire! I hope the USA intervenes militarily in Iran to save the lives of an innocent Iranian population. It is a 'golden' opportunity, not just for 'real politik', but to show the world America stills cares about freedom. The Iranian people are practically begging us to get involved. Whether it succeeds or fails doesn't matter- the action would have powerful symbolic value. And though Homer said "the rule of many is not good", you could not tell this by the alacrity of the crowds in Iran. Now is the contest!'
8. 'Truly, I, ... saw these things in my vision.'
9. 'Garret, with his frequent travels to Asia, was more than merely a man for all seasons- for that matter- he was a man for all condoms!'
10. 'With ease and celerity...'
11. 'He was certainly imbued more with Godly virtue than he was deficient in the royal purple.'
12. 'When I taught in South Korea, it is hard to say I neglected the mysteries of the Orient.'
13. 'When I was at University, 529CE was the date floating around for the end of late antiquity, and this marked the day when Justinian closed the schools of Philosophy in Athens and throughout the Roman empire. 550CE is the date used by Goffart and others to mark the emergence of Frankish power and the close of late antiquity. Some, such as Jones, see the death of Maurice in 602CE and the collapse of relative stability in the Byzantine Empire as the date for the close of late antiquity, especially in the East. While Brown and others point to the consolidation of Islam and the collapse of the Sassanid empire by 750CE as the true date for the final chapter in late antiquity. We can laughingly retort 'the Consolidation of Islam?' We might as well use the *Consolidation of Philosophy*, written in 524 CE at Pavia when Boethius was awaiting execution by the Ostrogoths, as the closing date. Why choose the date for the rise of the heathen cradle?'

14. 'The fall of Khomeini will be remembered as one of the greatest events since the days of the apostles.'
15. 'If America invades Iran, I hope our forces will remember the maxim of that great Socratic disciple (Cicero) when he said: *'We do not live for ourselves alone!'* Because if we are not on this earth to help, then what are we doing here? It is not merely that justice should precede charity but that *charity is justice*. It is not merely that money makes the world go round, but compassion as well, as evidenced when I give my cat Nieve a warm hug on a winter night.'
16. 'The early history of Scotland reaches back through the mists of time, whether Scot or Pict.'
17. 'Mountjoy in County Tyrone is just six miles from Drumnakilly in Ireland, the former near the Omagh area. The former is the area of settlement in 1611 for Andrew Stewart, Lord Ochiltree, arriving on a royal charter from England, and the latter is where the Gibboney's originated from. The Gibboney's were related to the Kyles of Scotland, also of noble peerage, like the Ochiltrees.'
18. 'The Boyd Family was the clan who destroyed Ochiltree Castle. Ochiltree House was built on the site of the ruins of the castle. The clan system in Scotland, came to an end, in 1746.'
19. 'James IV and many of the Scottish nobles were defeated at Flodden Field in 1513. All was lost save honor.'
20. 'King James I, son of Robert III., by the advice of the Romish prelates, determined to take from the nobles, all their power in the state. They had assumed almost regal power and authority, but were now deprived of many of their ancient privileges, and a number of the most influential, stripped of honors, wealth and political influence; some driven into exile. These men were not made of the stuff tamely to submit to this degradation. Their social power, based on clan spirit, and affection of the people, remained... Enraged at the ecclesiastical influence over the king, they were soon in the midst of a deadly contest, between the Scottish aristocracy, and the Scottish church, which lasted for thirty-two years, and finally concluded with the triumph of the nobles, who, in 1560, completely overthrew the Romish church in Scotland, and destroyed the Scottish hierarchy.'
21. 'Brian lived for many years, like a Scotsman on the dole- minus the alcohol.'
22. 'After living in Mexico for almost 20 years, I achieved my goal of learning Spanglish.'
23. 'My writings during the Mexican Drug War were *akin* to a Silesian Mystic during the Thirty Year's War.'
24. "If Trump can issue a Tariff check, then maybe Ramos will issue a weed check?"
25. 'City corruption feeds the professions: prostitution and drug-dealing.'
26. 'Mayte was keen to penetrate the *arcana* of Brian 's personal life.'
27. 'My leg injury from the military looked like I had stumbled across caltrops during a medieval battle.'
28. 'Born to wealth and Plutocracy...'
29. 'I abjured all passes from the same sex and welcomed invitations from the right women. You need to understand mankind *qua* Valentine.'

30. 'Let us all observe the *golden mean*, and believe with the poet, that
"God is paid when man receives... T' enjoy is to obey¹:"
For let not the Christian Religion be doubted, because too many of the wicked or
profligate approach the holy altar!'
31. 'From paradise Mani has come! Rejoice brothers! From paradise the gate was
opened to you O' brothers of the right hand. A Light day it has become for us.
From the prosperous paradise the gate was opened by the gods: garland, helmet,
and diadem do we display with full honor. Grant me my most pious wish... that I
may walk in the eternal light paradise.'
32. 'The Chortitza tree in Ukraine symbolized a golden age for Russian
Mennonites, representing prosperity and privilege up until the time of the
October Revolution. It currently stands on the Ukrainian side of the front line in
the Russia-Ukraine War. The tree is said to be 700 years old and dying, not
unlike Ukraine itself. Let us hope that Ukraine can still thrive in this- the tree's
twilight. Let us hope it's passing does not symbolize the death of Ukraine.'
33. 'As Pliny the Younger might say, 'only few of my poems have broke their
prison and escaped to light!'
34. 'Here's some seedy stuff. There was a sign above the *Bordello*. It read,
'steady as she blows!'
35. 'Heimat: a nostalgia for the bucolic and idyllic.'

¹ Alexander Pope.